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AN APPLICATION OF CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS ON HUMAN INTENTION PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

Due to the rapidly increasing need of human-robot interaction (HRI), more intelligent robots are in demand. However, the vast majority of robots can only follow strict instructions, which seriously restricts their flexibility and versatility. A critical fact that strongly negates the experience of HRI is that robots cannot understand human intentions. This study aims at improving the robotic intelligence by training it to understand human intentions. Different from previous studies that recognizing human intentions from distinctive actions, this paper introduces a method to predict human intentions before a single action is completed. The experiment of throwing a ball towards designated targets are conducted to verify the effectiveness of the method. The proposed deep learning based method proves the feasibility of applying convolutional neural networks (CNN) under a novel circumstance. Experiment results show that the proposed CNN-vote method out competes three traditional machine learning techniques. In current context, the CNN-vote predictor achieves the highest testing accuracy with relatively less data needed.

KEYWORDS

Human-robot Interaction; Intentions Prediction; Convolutional Neural Networks;

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APPLICATION OF BIG DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERNET OF THINGS TO THE INTELLIGENT ACTIVE ROBOTIC PROSTHESIS FOR TRANSFEMORAL AMPUTEES

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ABSTRACT

With the advent and rising usage of Internet of Things (IoT) eco-systems, there is a consequent, parallel rise in opportunities where technology can find its place to improve a number of human conditions. However, this is nothing new - we have been perfecting the usage of tools to aid our daily living throughout history. The true evolution lies in the interaction between us and the tools we create. Tools are now smart devices, yielding an opportunity where human-device interaction is giving us the very knowledge on how to improve that particular synthesis. From improving our fitness to detecting bradycardia and response of traumatic brain injury patient, we have come to a point where we are able to gain actionable insight into a lot of aspects of our health and condition. This creates a certain autonomy in understanding the unique make-up of every single person, in addition to yielding information that can be used by health practitioners to help in diagnosis, determination of medical approach and right recovery and follow-up methods. All of this supported by two major factors: IoT platforms and Big Data Analysis (BDA).

This paper takes a deep dive into exemplary set-up of IoT platform and BDA framework necessary to support the improvement of human condition. Our SmartLeg prosthetic device integrates advanced prosthetic and robotic technology with the state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms capable of adapting the working of the prosthesis to the optimal gait and power consumption patterns, which provide means to customize the device to a particular user

KEYWORDS

Human-machine interface, active robotic prosthesis, machine learning, big data analysis.

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CUSTOMER OPINIONS EVALUATION: A CASE STUDY ON ARABIC TWEETS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an automatic method for extracting, processing, and analysis of customer opinions on Arabic social media. We present a four-step approach for mining of Arabic tweets. First, Natural Language Processing (NLP) with different types of analyses had performed. Second, we present an automatic and expandable lexicon for Arabic adjectives. The initial lexicon is built using 1350 adjectives as seeds from processing of different datasets in Arabic language. The lexicon is automatically expanded by collecting synonyms and morphemes of each word through Arabic resources and google translate. Third, emotional analysis was considered by two different methods; Machine Learning (ML) and rule based method. Finally, Feature Selection (FS) is also considered to enhance the mining results. The experimental results reveal that the proposed method outperforms counterpart ones with an improvement margin of up to 4% using F-Measure.

KEYWORDS

Opinion Mining - Arabic - Bag of Words - Feature Selection - Emotions- Adjective Lexicons.

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A HYBRID LEARNING ALGORITHM IN AUTOMATED TEXT CATEGORIZATION OF LEGACY DATA

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this research is to develop an algorithm to automatically classify measurement types from NASA's airborne measurement data archive. The product has to meet specific metrics in term of accuracy, robustness and usability, as the initial decision-tree based development has shown limited applicability due to its resource intensive characteristics. We have developed an innovative solution that is much more efficient while offering comparable performance. Similar to many industrial applications, the data available are noisy and correlated; and there is a wide range of features that are associated with the type of measurement to be identified. The proposed algorithm uses a decision tree to select features and determine their weights. A weighted Naive Bayes is used due to the presence of highly correlated inputs. The development has been successfully deployed in an industrial scale, and the results show that the development is well-balanced in term of performance and resource requirements

KEYWORDS

Classification, machine learning, atmospheric measurement.

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TRANSFER LEARNING WITH CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR IRIS RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Iris is one of the common biometrics used for identity authentication. It has the potential to recognize persons with a high degree of assurance. Extracting effective features is the most important stage in the iris recognition system. Different features have been used to perform iris recognition system. A lot of them are based on hand-crafted features designed by biometrics experts. According to the achievement of deep learning in object recognition problems, the features learned by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) have gained great attention to be used in the iris recognition system. In this paper, we proposed an effective iris recognition system by using transfer learning with Convolutional Neural Networks. The proposed system is implemented by fine-tuning a pre-trained convolutional neural network (VGG-16) for features extracting and classification. The performance of the iris recognition system is tested on four public databases IITD, iris databases CASIA-Iris-V1, CASIA-Iris-thousand and, CASIA-Iris-Interval. The results show that the proposed system is achieved a very high accuracy rate.

KEYWORDS

Biometrics, iris, recognition, deep learning, convolutional neural network (CNN), transfer learning.

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A SMART BRAIN CONTROLLED WHEELCHAIR BASED MICROCONTROLLER SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper is to build Smart Brain Controlled wheelchair (SBCW) intended for patient of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS). Brain control interface (BCI) gave solutions for a patients having a low rate of data exchange, also by using the BCI the user should have the ability to meditate and tension to let the signal get received. Using the BCI continuously is very much exhausted for the patients, The proposed system is trying to give all handicapped people and ALS patients the simplest way to let them have a life at least near to the normal life. The system will mainly depend on the Electroencephalogram (EEG) signals and also on the Electromyography (EMG) signals to put the system in command and out of command. The system will interface with user through a tablet and it will be secured by sensors and tracking system to avoid any obstacle. The proposed system is safe and easily built with lower cost compared with other similar systems.

KEYWORDS

Smart Brain Controlled wheelchair (SBCW), Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), Brain control interface, Brain Computer Interface (BCI), Electroencephalogram EEG, Electromyography EMG.

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